

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D3.6 ANALYTICS ON THE SUBMITTED PROPOSALS: OPEN CALL 2

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this public report is to provide a summary of relevant statistics and findings from STADIEM Open Call #2. The information will be published on the website of the project.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The STADIEM Open Call #2 was officially announced on the STADIEM website and social media accounts, as well as on the F6S platform, on December 25, 2021, at 12:00 CET, and it was closed on February 28, 2022, at 17:00 CET.

This open call aimed to attract and engage 40 promising tech start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs to join the STADIEM 4-stage pilot programme, with a duration of 14 months and a budget of 1,93M EUR.

The target was start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs with innovative products and high-scaling and piloting potential whose solutions can be integrated/ incorporated in the European corporate / media sector and beyond, thus developing new products and services which address current media challenges as identified in the STADIEM Open Call #2 Guide for Applicants.

This document provides a summary of the achieved results including relevant statistics and findings from Open Call #2 and will be published on STADIEM website.

2 OPEN CALL 2 STATISTICS

The second STADIEM Open Call was automatically closed on February 28, 17:00 CET (Brussels time). In total 179 applications were started on the F6S platform, and 115 proposals have been finally submitted as presented in the chart below.

FIGURE 1 OPEN CALL RESULTS: FINALISED OR IN PROGRES

2.1 PROFILE OF APPLICANTS

2.1.1 Countries

The second open call received proposals from 26 countries. It is possible to see a predominance of applications from the UK (20), Germany (17), Belgium (7) and the Netherlands (7), followed by applications from Spain, France, and Italy among others. A large number of countries were covered thanks to the communication and dissemination efforts in getting participants from all the eligible countries.

The geographical distribution of the submitted application is shown in the chart below.

FIGURE 2 NUMBER OF APPLICATIONS PER COUNTRY

2.1.2 STADIEM Selected Focus Areas

In this second Open Call, STADIEM allowed for applications within 7 established focus areas. Applicants were able to select between Archiving, Content Creation & Distribution, Content Verification and Fight Against Disinformation, Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media, Journalism 4.0, Monetisation and Moonshots (any new existing and interesting solutions related to media).

The distribution of applications received among the different focus areas can be seen in the figure below, which shows Content Creation and Distribution as the challenge chosen by most applicants (43,5%), followed by Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media (20,9%), Monetization (13%), Journalism 4.0 (9,6%), Moonshots (5,2%), Content verification and against disinformation (5,2%) and Archiving (2,6%).

FIGURE 3 DISTRIBUTION OF APPLICATIONS PER FOCUS AREA

2.1.3 Maturity Level

In the second Open Call, applicants had to provide information about their current product status and maturity level. As shown in the figure below, the majority of applications have a private beta MVP (24,3%), fully functional product with paying customers (23,5%), and recurring MRR (20,9%).

FIGURE 4 TECHNOLOGICAL LEVEL: CURRENT PRODUCT STATUS

2.1.4 Business Type

The STADIEM's second open call is requested for applicants whose business model is mainly B2B or in the case of B2C, they have B2B partnerships.

As indicated in the figure below, almost all applicants managed to fulfil the requirement.

FIGURE 5 APPLICANTS PER TYPE OF BUSINESS

2.2 SELECTED PROPOSALS

After the evaluation process, 40 proposals have been selected from the 115 submitted (34,7%). It is worthy to note that 9 proposals were deemed not eligible, hence the selection was done on the basis of 106 startups.

2.2.1 Summary of selected proposals

The 40 selected proposals were among 17 eligible countries, established mainly in the EU and other H2020 eligible countries.

FIGURE 6 AWARDEE PER COUNTRY

The focus areas addressed by the awardees reflect the overall distribution of the different focus areas, with the majority covering Content Creation & Distribution (40%) and Data/AI/ML/Synthetic Media (25%).

FIGURE 7 DISTRIBUTION OF AWARDEES PER FOCUS AREA

The majority of the awardees in the second open call already have a recurring MRR (37,5%), and a fully functional product with several with paying customers (25%)

FIGURE 8 AWARDEE TECHNOLOGICAL LEVEL

All the selected companies are B2B operational, with a 10% that also provide a B2C solution, as illustrated in the graphic below.

FIGURE 9 DISTRIBUTION OF AWARDEES FOR TYPE OF SOLUTION

Most of the selected companies are relatively young – being operational for 2-4 years, however we still have 7 of them that have been operational for 8 years or more. An overview is provided in the figure below.

FIGURE 10 OPERATIONAL YEARS OF AWARDEES

